

Developing Self-Assessment Instruments Of Affective Domain On Belief And Morality (Aqidah Akhlak) Subject

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 14, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: December 16, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Instrument, Self-Assessment, Affective Domain, Aqidah Akhlak, Madrasah Tsanawiyah</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14501191</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to find a valid and reliable self-assessment procedure and instrument to measure the spiritual and social attitude domain of Belief and Morality (Aqidah Akhlak) subject in Madrasah Tsanawiyah by implementing Borg & Gall's research and development model. The content validity of the instruments was analysed by using Aiken formula, and the construct validity used Explanatory Factor Analysis (EFA), while the instrument reliability was conducted by using Alpha Cronbach. The results showed that the content validity and the construct validity of the instrument were valid. In addition, there was a positive relationship between morality to Allah and the Messenger of Allah towards the morality to parents, teachers, themselves, and others. Due to the implementation of 2013 Curriculum which demands multi-technique instruments to measure comprehensive learning outcomes, the instrument developed in this research can be used as a reference and consideration for teachers in developing instruments as a learning outcome evaluation in the affective domain (spiritual and social attitude domain). The instruments can be used to measure the achievement of learning outcomes regarding the affective domain in Madrasah Tsanawiyah or the equivalent.</i></p>

Introduction

Aqidah (belief) and akhlak (morality) are the substance of Islamic law. Aqidah is the foundation and the base of faith; in addition, akhlak (morality) is a manifestation of faith in the behavior or good deeds. Akhlak (Moral) Education is a discourse that is never endin learning process, using various names, such as ethical education (Curriculum 2013).

The main principle of curriculum development in 2013 is based on a competence-based curriculum model with standards of graduate's competence (SKL) set for one unit of education, education level and educational program. In addition to having the main principles, 2013 curriculum has three aspects of assessment, namely aspects of knowledge, aspects of skills, and aspects of attitudes and behaviors. The three aspects of the assessment are then outlined in four core competencies (KI) such as core competence 1 (KI.1) namely the spiritual domain, core competence 2 (KI.2) such as the domain of social attitudes, core competence 3 (KI.3) such as the cognitive domain and core competence 4 (KI.4) such as the psychomotor domain.

The structure of the affective domain as developed by Krathwohl et al. (1986) is quite complicated; it means that the affective structure of elements is quite complex, not all affective characteristics should be evaluated in schools. Some affective characteristics that need to be considered (measured and assessed) related to islamic education subjects in schools such as attitudes, interests, self-concepts, and values (Dikdasmen, 2003).

The main challenges is human development (human resource development) in addition to natural resources. Qualified human resources are not only in the form of intelligence and skills but also attitude and mentality. The demands of the development of the evaluation system are strengthening in the group of subjects of Religious Education and Noble Morals. The subjects of Religious Education and Noble Morals are considered as the main leading factors of other subject groups to help students to have internalization of religious education and accustomed to noble behavior in addition to be smart, skilled, and creative.

In the context of Islamic religious education, the development of learning evaluation is emphasized in the affective domain (Solichin, M, 2007) which is how the evaluation is directed to know the extent to which the passions, awards, and behaviors of learners have been in accordance with two main sources of Islam, namely in the Qur'an and as-Sunnah. Al-Abrasyi (1987) emphasized the aspect of moral education is very important for islamic education objective. Education and teaching process are not fulfilling the brains of students with all kinds of knowledge that they do not know, but educating their morals and souls, instilling a sense of fadhilah (virtue), familiarizing them with high modesty, preparing them for a holy life and having sincerity and honesty.

The main purpose of education is summarized in one word "fadhilah" (virtue) with the main mission sent by Muhammad as a prophet to complete morality (Innamaa bu 'istu liutammima makaarim al-akhlaaq) (al-Syaibani, 1979). But in fact, in implementing 2013 Curriculum and the assessment system, this cognitive goal has been

prioritized in education in Indonesia, many educators are not concerned about other domains, the teachers have not fully understood the assessment system (Retnawati et al., 2016) because the assessment of the implementation of 2013 Curriculum. Based on the observations of the authors in several Madrasah Tsanawiyah, there are still a lot of handbooks or Student Worksheets (LKS) used as learning evaluation materials that only emphasize on the cognitive aspects, the student performance related to psychomotor and affective competencies are often overlooked. Hall, R.A (2011) stated that affective assessment, which is often overlooked in learning practice, whereas the educators can provide a complete and relevant educational experience and attractive learning process to students. According to Suyanto (2010), ignoring the affective domain harms the development of learners both individual and society as a whole. Students know a lot about something, but lack of attitude, interest, value system and positive appreciation of what they know.

The learning of Aqidah Akhlak is inseparable from the implementation of evaluations conducted by the teachers. According to the objective conditions in the field during the study, there is a tendency of Aqidah Akhlak do not emphasize the purpose of the evaluation itself. One of the contributing factors is the lack of teachers to carry out the evaluations in a varied and continuous manner, because they pursue the targets that must be achieved regardless the expected quality of the material, so that the students' ability in affective competencies is neglected.

Teachers realize that the affective domain (spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes) is important in the learning of Aqidah Akhlak. However, in fact, on its strength, most teachers do not assess the affective domain (the domain of spiritual and social attitudes) and psychomotor domain implements relevant instruments. The assessment does not have a clear reference and is considered to have been assessed unstructured and planned instrument.

The quality of educational evaluation in Madrasah Tsanawiyah in general is inseparable from the quality of the use of relevant assessment instruments, for cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. Speaking of assessment instruments certainly cannot be separated from how to develop assessment devices on the three aspects. Assessments conducted on these three aspects will result in the students who do not only master the knowledge, but also have a commendable attitude and morality.

The reality of evaluation instruments that are currently widely used by teachers of Akhlak is evaluation in the cognitive domain, concrete manifestations of the achievement of student learning outcomes in a number of subjects are measured based on test results. The instrument developed has not measured the substance, namely measuring changes in the faith (spiritual) and behavior or social attitudes of students, so that the instrument of evaluation of the affective domain (spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes) of moral religious subjects in madrasah tsanawiyah needs to be developed.

Self Evaluation

Self-evaluation refers to an individual's basic evaluation of abilities and competence (Peng et al., 2016; Bourke, 2017; Yan, 2019). In the context of an institution, self-evaluation is an evaluation conducted by the institution to collect the data, data analysis, and interpretation of results used for planning, development, improvement and/ or improvement of the institution's performance (Nuchron et al., 2013). At this point, the institution's improvement relates to the theories and research regarding the strategies for the positive changes on educational system to achieve the goals (Mekhlafi & Osman, 2019). Self-evaluation is used to explore, understand, and be well aware of the institution's profile, including quality, and current institutional conditions to be used as a basis for the institution to determine the target or desired future conditions (Nuchron et al., 2013). According to Hofman et al (O'Brien et al., 2015) self-evaluation in institutions, for example, is seen in school self-evaluation where the evaluation is an internal process used to ensure quality and improve the teaching and learning process and school performance. Self-evaluation is used as a key requirement for school improvement (Smith & McCully, 2013). According to Bollaert et al (Alzamil, 2014), self-evaluation in educational institutions is an important need and tool in improving the performance of institutions to achieve a highly competitive position.

Self-evaluation has been stimulated as a way to encourage sustainable quality improvement (Van der Bij et al., 2016; Carroll, 2020; To & Panadero, 2019). Self-evaluation is one of the important aspects in the overall accreditation cycle with various roles and uses, including quality assurance (Sopingi et al., 2015). Self-evaluation becomes a milestone of a development, where development is a planned change so it is necessary to understand how to conduct a comprehensive, structured and systematic self-evaluation so that the results can be used as a basis in the planning process in order to achieve the desired goals, namely sustainable quality improvement (Luqman, 2017). The principle of implementation of goal-oriented self-evaluation, referring to the criteria of success, the principle of benefits, and objectives; or in other words, the purpose of self-evaluation is implemented in reference to the goal to be achieved (Nuchron et al., 2013). Therefore, through self-evaluation, it can be seen the advantages and disadvantages that further this deficiency becomes the purpose of improvement.

Affective Learning

According to Mosby's Medical Dictionary, affective learning is defined through learning skills and in particular as the acquisition of behaviors that express feelings in attitude, appreciation, and value (Bamidis, 2017). This is in line with Krathwohl et al's opinion that defines affective learning as an object that emphasizes the tone of

feelings, emotions, or students' acceptance or rejection of subject matter (Gupta & Pandey, 2018; Kulkarni et al., 2018). Meanwhile specifically, Hatfiel et al (Webster et al., 2013) define affective learning as the main proposed educational focus for guiding student approach/avoidance behaviors related to subject matter content. In other words, affective learning is a learning that relates to the interests, attitudes and motivations of learners (Bamidis, 2017). In affective learning, the domain of learning according to Mottet & Beebe (Webster et al., 2013) covers the underlying attitudes, beliefs, values, and emotions and is related to the knowledge and skills they are acquiring. Therefore, affective in learning relates to value that is difficult to measure because it relates to the awareness of the person (Fatimah Kadir, 2015).

Krathwohl et al regulate the domain of affection during the learning process in five levels, namely (1) accepting (described as willingness to attend an event or event), (2) responding (learners are willing to react and participate in an activity), (3) assessing (the intention to accept or reject the event by positively or negatively), (4) organizing (when learners have the ability to determine which values are more dominant), (5) complex values (when learners decide to act in accordance with the accepted by respecting and making that practice or attitude part of their personality) (Phan, 2019; Fong & DeWitt, 2019). According to Duncan-Wehitt (Omar et al., 2015), affective learning can evoke feelings such as threats or pleasure depending on the learner's learning experience. Therefore, according to Vermunt and Vermetten, affective learning outcomes are the feelings that arise during learning process that create an emotional state that may positively, neutrally or negatively affect the learning process (Duchatelet et al., 2018). Thus, affective learning is more related to attitudes that emphasize how a person chooses and sorts an action and considers whether the chosen one is beneficial or causes problems (Alifah, 2019).

Student Competence (Character)

Competence is the underlying characteristic of a person in relation to the performance activities of an individual in his work or the basic character that has a causal relationship with the criteria referred to (Purwati, 2016). In the context of education, learning objectives are formulated based on indicators of the competency achievement including cognitive, affective, and psychomotor competencies (Diani, 2015; Patmawati et al., 2020; Amalia & Suwatno, 2016) so that all subjects taught and studied must contribute to the formation of core competencies that are expected through the teaching and learning process. In other words, student competence is defined as each individual's ability to integrate knowledge, skills, and attitudes in accepting and practicing learning (Baartman & De Bruijn, 2011; Lapisa et al., 2017) so that the learning process can help the students establish higher level of thinking (Nadarajan et al., 2020). Students' competence is obtained after experiencing treatment that includes aspects of knowledge, attitudes, and skills (Ayu et al., 2016). Furthermore, the students have an important role to foster their learning process (Nasri et al., 2020). Thus, during the learning process, there must be efforts to nurture and increase students' motivation in learning so that the students can be encouraged to improve their abilities (Nur, 2018).

Competency supports the creation of character development of each student to improve the competence, skills and understanding of the learning process (Baartman & De Bruijn, 2011). One of the indicators of competency is to create character development which is seen in educational objectives that not only focus on skills and knowledge that boils down to the creativity and competence of students in understanding science and science, but also focuses on instilling morality and ethics into students who bear fruit on good moral attitudes in the midst of society in the future (Sutjipto, 2014). In line with this, competence in character formation is also seen in the domain of affective learning, in which according to Supardi competencies include characteristics of responsibility, cooperation, discipline, commitment, confidence, honesty in respecting the opinions of others, as well as the ability to control themselves where the form of assessment in the affective domain can use non-test instruments (Alifah, 2019). Therefore, in order to realize this goal, there are the needs to be a harmonious synergy between students, teachers, and school managers (Permatasari et al, 2013).

Method

This research used a type of research and development (R&D). Research and development method is a research method used to produce the product of affective self-assessment instrument (spiritual domain and social attitude domain), and test the effectiveness of the product. Borg and Gall (1983) explained, "The purpose of R & D is to bridge the gap that frequently exist between educational research and educational practice".

Field Testing

The design of the field testings to develop self-assessment instruments in the spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes of Aqidah Akhlak Subjects in Madrasah Tsanawiyah in this study used five main steps, they are: (1) drafting the preliminary instrument (phase one), (2) conducting limited field testings in three Madrasah Tsanawiyah, (3) evaluating and revising phase one, (4) conducting wider field testings in fifteen Madrasah Tsanawiyah, and to (5) evaluating and revising phase 2. The five main steps are visualized as follows.

Research Design

This research conducted research and development model (R&D) using Borg and Gall model (1983) with 10 development steps. They are: research and information collecting, planning, develop preliminary form of

product, preliminary field testing, main product revision, main field testing, operational product revision, operational field testing, final product revision, dan dissemination and implementation.

Population and Sample/ Study Group/ Participants

The instrument test subjects consisted of teachers and students of Madrasah Tsanawiyah in 3 former residences in Central Java such as Former Semarang Residences, Former Pekalongan Residences and Former Banyumas Residences as well as the Madrasah Tsanawiyah in Yogyakarta and Bantul Regions. The test subjects can be presented in table 1.

Table 1

List of instrument test subjects

No	School Name	Description
1	MTs N 1 Banyumas	Field Testing I
2	MTs NU Purwokerto	Field Testing I
3	MTs Muhammadiyah Purwokerto	Field Testing I
4	MTs N 1 Kendal	Field Testing II
5	MTs NU 01 Cepiring Kendal	Field Testing II
6	MTs Muhammadiyah 1 Weleri Kendal	Field Testing II
7	MTs N 1 Tegal	Field Testing II
8	MTs NU Wakhid Hasyim Talang Tegal	Field Testing II
9	MTs Muhammadiyah Dukuhturi Tegal	Field Testing II
10	MTs N 1 Banyumas	Field Testing II
11	MTs Muhammadiyah 1 Purwokerto	Field Testing II
12	MTs NU 1 Purwokerto	Field Testing II
13	MTs N 1 Kota Yogyakarta	Field Testing II
14	MTs Nurul Ummah Kota Gede Yogyakarta	Field Testing II
15	MTs Muhammadiyah 1 Kota Yogyakarta	Field Testing II
16	MTs N 1 Bantul	Field Testing II
17	MTs NU 1 Bantul	Field Testing II
18	MTs Muhammadiyah 1 Bantul	Field Testing II

Data Collection Tools

The data collected consisted of quantitative data supported by qualitative data. Quantitative data was data of instrument test results in the form of guidelines / observation guides for teachers and questionnaires for students (Reflection Sheet). While qualitative data in the form of a collection of information in the form of words that were supporting data in this study.

Data Collection

At the planning stage, researchers conducted an in-depth exploration on madrasah Tsanawiyah curriculum focused on Aqidah Akhlak subjects. Afterwards, the theories of affective domain evaluation (spiritual and social attitudes) were investigated. At this stage of planning the main data collection technique implemented was documentation. At the test phase in the field, both in the first and second stage of the instruments tested were the scale of attitudes in the form of observation guidelines and questionnaires. Observation guidelines were intended for teachers in making observations on student attitudes, while questionnaires were used to measure student attitudes based on student perception and recognition or in other terms self report and teacher assessment. The researchers observed teachers and students and randomly interview teachers or students to find out what they thought about the instruments being developed. The instrument was equipped with minutes of meeting that must be filled by the teacher during the field testing.

Data Analysis

Instrument analysis was performed twice; they were analysis of field testing on phase I and analysis of field testing on phase II. The purpose of the first field testing which was also called as preliminary try out (Hadari&Martin, 1995) was directed to: know the face validity, check the possibility of an instrument that is not clear, examine the possibility of foreign words or terms so that it is not understood, examine the possibility of instruments that were too shallow in revealing indicators of achievement, and examining the possibility of instruments that were not relevant to the information they wanted to disclose as indicators of learning outcomes. Empirically, testing the suitability of items with the grid (construct) could be tested with a total-item correlation analysis to see the contribution of items to the total variable. By calculating correlation between attribute groups, it can be obtained the discriminant validity (Munir, Abdul Razak, 2005). Items that measure the same attribute are expected to have a high correlation index, while items that measure different attributes have a low correlation index. Instruments that are able to make measurements carefully with a low level of measurement error will provide relatively consistent and stable measurement results (Purwanto, 2010).

Empirical validity testing is conducted with a factor analysis to determine the construct through The Explanatory Factor Analysis (EFA) conducted through SPSS 23 in which if the KMO value is more than 0.50 and the anti-

image correlation is more than 0.30 then it can be said that the instrument has met the construct (Munir, Abdul Razak, 2005). While the reliability coefficient is conducted using Alpha Cronbach through SPSS 23.0.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary Product Design

There are four steps in the preparation of the initial design, namely: identification of objectives or measuring areas, operationalization of concepts into behavioral indicators, writing of statement items, and review of statement items.

Field Testing and The Results of Phase I Testing

The field testing was conducted in 3 madrasa tsanawiyah, namely MTs Negeri 1 Banyumas, MTs Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, and MTs Ma'arif NU 01 Purwokerto. The instrument tested consisted of self-assessment of the spiritual domain and self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes as well as the assessment of the teacher's observation of the spiritual domain and social attitudes (affective domain). Before the field testing, the author coordinated and conducted simulations with all teachers of moral religious subjects in 3 Madrasah Tsanawiyah on the technique of using instruments. The technique of using instruments for grade VII, VIII and grade IX students is self-assessment spiritual domain and self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes, each 10 students at each grade level, so that each school there are 30 students multiplied by 3 MTs, so that there are 90 students, then the teacher gives an explanation and guides students in choosing instrument answers according to the real conditions of students spontaneously. In terms of observation assessment instrument given to teachers of Aqidah Akhlak in MTs N 1 Banyumas, they were 3 people, teachers of Aqidah Akhlak in MTs Ma'arif NU 1 Purwokerto Barat and 1 teacher at MTs Muhammadiyah Purwokerto.

Table 2

Test results of phase I: Instrument of self-assessment on spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes Grade VII Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs)

Assessment Type	Reliability	Number of items	Correlation items – Minimum Total of 0.3
Self-assessment on Spiritual Domain	0,83	93 items	85 items
Self-assessment on Social Attitudes Domain	0,96	92 items	85 items

Based on the overall points of question, the instrument of spiritual self-assessment with the total of 93 items are valid and reliable for 85 items because all the index of alpha reliability above 0.3. Meanwhile, regarding the invalid and reliable items, there are 8 items namely items no, 18, 27, 39, 43, 57, 62, 71 and 83, because all alpha reliability indexes are below 0.3. While the instrument of self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes showed that 92 items that are valid and reliable for 85 items because all indexes of alpha readability above 0.3. Meanwhile, in terms of the invalid and reliable items, there are 7 items namely items no, 22, 34, 45, 59, 67, 75 and 88, because all indexes of Alpha reliability are below 0.3. The overall reliability average of both types of assessment was 0.896. By using the minimum correlation criteria of each item with a total score of 0.3, then the points of the question that have a correlation of less than 0.3 must be issued. By conducting reliability testing repeatedly by removing items that have an index below 0.30 obtained reliable instrument items while improving the overall reliability of the instrument. The items are excluded because they are below 0.3; then, it needs to be revised before the next phase of field testing. The test results of grade VII instrument self-assessment spiritual domain have a reliability of 0.834 then the instrument belongs to a very high category. While the results of the grade VII field testing of social attitudes self-assessment instrument has a reliability of 0.825 then the instrument belongs to the category of very high.

From the results of the evaluation instrument on field testing by means of spiritual domain self-assessment, and self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes, grade VIII MTs in phase I, the overall reliability of the instrument is as follows.

Table 3

Test results of phase I: Instrument of self-assessment on spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes, Grade VIII Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs)

Assessment Type	Reliability	Number of items	Correlation items – Minimum Total of 0.3
Self-assessment on Spiritual Domain	0,98	120 items	100 items
Self-assessment on Social Attitudes Domain	0,96	119 items	100 items

According to the overall points of the question, the instrument of spiritual self-assessment of the spiritual domain consisting of 120 items that are valid and reliable 100 items because all the index of alpha reliability above 0.3, while the invalid and reliable there are 20 items namely items number 3, 7, 11, 18, 23, 28, 32, 39, 43, 46, 51, 57, 63, 69, 71, 77, 83, 96, 113 and 118, because all Alpha reliability indexes are below 0.3. As a self-assessment instrument in the domain of social attitudes amounting to 119 items that are valid and reliable 100 items because all the index of alpha reliability above 0.3, while the invalid and reliable there are 19 items namely point number 6, 12, 22, 27, 31, 34, 45, 48, 51, 59, 60, 67.72, 75, 85, 92, 103, 112 and 115, as all Alpha reliability indexes are below 0.3. The overall reliability average of both types of assessment was 0.964. By using the minimum correlation criteria of each item with a total score of 0.3, then the points of the question that have a correlation of less than 0.3 must be excluded. By conducting reliability testing repeatedly by removing items that have an index below 0.30 obtained reliable instrument items while improving the overall reliability of the instrument. The items are excluded because below 0.3 need to be revised before the next phase of field testing. The results of the grade VIII field testing of spiritual domain self-assessment have a reliability of 0.976 then the instrument belongs to a very high category. The results of the grade VIII field testing of social attitudes self-assessment have a reliability of 0.951 then the instrument belongs to a very high category.

From the results of the test instrument evaluation of the affective domain by means of spiritual self-assessment and self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes, in grade IX MTs in stage 1, the overall reliability of the instrument is as follows.

Table 4

Test results of phase I: Instrument of self-assessment on spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes Grade IX MTs

Assessment Type	Reliability	Number of items	Correlation items – Minimum Total of 0.3
Self-assessment on Spiritual Domain	0,77	92 items	85 items
Self-assessment on Social Attitudes Domain	0,96	102 items	90 items

Investigating the overall points of the question, the instrument of spiritual domain self-assessment consisting of 92 items that are valid and reliable for 85 points because all alpha reliability index is above 0.3, while the invalid and reliable are 7 items namely items number 17, 22, 35, 47, 64, 73 and 89, because all alpha reliability indexes are below 0.3. While the instrument of self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes consisting of 102 items that are valid and reliable for 90 items because all the index of alpha reliability above 0.3, while the invalid and reliable items are 12 items namely item number: 35, 39, 42, 47, 52, 57, 61, 63, 75, 85, 91, and 112, because all the alpha reliability index is below 0.3. The overall reliability average of both types of assessments was 0.864. By using the minimum correlation criteria of each item with a total score of 0.3, then the points of the question that have a correlation of less than 0.3 must be excluded. By conducting reliability testing repeatedly removing items that have an index below 0.30, it was obtained reliable instrument items and at the same time improving the overall reliability of the instrument. The items are excluded because below 0.3 need to be revised before the next phase of field testing. The results of the grade IX field testing assessment of the spiritual domain have a reliability of 0.773 then the instrument belongs to the high category. The results of the grade IX field testing of self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes have a reliability of 0.955 then the instrument belongs to a very high category.

Revising Preliminary Design

Based on the test results of grade VII, VIII and IX instruments, a number of items need to be revised before the phase II field testing. The initial design revision was conducted by removing instrument items that have an index below 0.30 so that reliable instrument items are obtained while improving the overall reliability of the instrument.

Product Design Phase II

This section described the instrument made in the second stage which includes the steps of preparation and the details of the questionnaire / scale. The first step is to review the objectives and measurement area by referring to the preparation of the instrument on stage one, namely the syllabus of moral religious subjects issued by the Ministry of Religious Affairs. The second step is the preparation of the instrument by considering the results of the preparation of the instrument as well as the first stage field testing. In the second phase, several changes and revisions were made by studying the undeveloped content and the items of the instrument that fell in phase one were revised.

Results of the Testing on Phase II

The implementation of the second phase of the field testing was expanded. The expansion was carried out by increasing the number of madrasahs used as well as the population taking of each madrasah. Instrument validity

testing is conducted with factor analysis. Before factor analysis, KMO and Barlett's tests were conducted to determine the feasibility of the instrument. The validity of the structure of the grade VII spiritual domain self-assessment instrument is done using EFA with a value of KMO = 0.649, self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes with a value of KMO = 0.706 and each item has an anti-image coefficient more than 0.5 which means it has met the requirements for factor analysis. The validity of the structure of the grade VIII spiritual domain self-assessment instrument is done using EFA with a value of KMO= 0.819, self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes with a value of KMO = 0.674 and each item has an anti-image coefficient more than 0.5 which means it has met the requirements for factor analysis. The validity of the structure of the grade IX spiritual domain self-assessment instrument is done using EFA with a value of KMO= 0.629, self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes with a value of KMO = 0.695 and each item has an anti-image coefficient more than 0.5 which means it has met the requirements for factor analysis. With the help of SPSS Version 23.0 application, for the reliability of the spiritual domain self-assessment instrument grade VII of 480 respondents Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.834, while the reliability of the instrument of self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes of 480 respondents Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.959. For the reliability of the instrument of self-assessment of the spiritual domain grade VIII of 450 respondents Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.976, while the reliability of the instrument of self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes of 450 respondents value Cronbach's Alpha 0.951. For the reliability of the instrument of spiritual self-assessment grade IX from 420 respondents Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.773, while the reliability of the instrument of self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes of 420 respondents Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.955.

Based on the data above when the reliability value of spiritual self-assessment instruments is recapitulated from grade VII, VIII and IX obtained an average of 0.861, the calculation result of $0.834 + 0.976 + 0.773 = 2.583$ divided by 3. While the average reliability value of the social attitude self-assessment instrument is 0.955, the calculation result of $0.959+0.951+0.955= 2.865$ is divided by 3.

Thus, the product in the form of an instrument of evaluation of the affective domain of AqidahAkhlak Subject both spiritual self-assessment and self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes has been proven and successfully developed.

The content of AqidahAkhlak in MTs includes the pillars of faith, namely faith in God, faith in angels, faith in the book, faith in the Messenger of God, faith in the Day of Resurrection and faith in qadha and qadhar. This aspect of religion becomes the basis for giving rise to morality to others. Morality to Allah and morality to the Messenger of Allah is the basis of faith that from both aspects gives rise to morality to the other. In other words, morality to parents, teachers, themselves, and others is a manifestation of morality to God and His Messenger. By associating between the aspects of morality to God and morality to the Messenger of God with four other aspects of morality, namely to parents, teachers, themselves, and others, the results of analysis for the answer to self-assessment of the spiritual domain can be visualized as follows.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that in developing the instrument of self-assessment evaluation of the affective domain (spiritual domain and the domain of social attitudes) in the subjects AqidahAkhlak in Madrasah Tsanawiyah includes instruments of self-assessment spiritual domain, and self-assessment area of social attitudes. The development of affective domain evaluation instruments is carried out in 10 steps, namely: (a) the study of AqidahAkhlak subject literature and the development of affective domain evaluation instruments in Madrasah Tsanawiyah; (b) review the competence standards of graduates (SKL), core competencies (KI) and basic competencies (KD) of AqidahAkhlak subjects; (c) development of learning outcome indicators; (d) selection of affective domain evaluation instruments; (e) drafting affective domain evaluation instruments; (f) phase one: field testing at 3 Madrasah Tsanawiyah; (g) evaluation and improvement of phase one test results; (h) phase two: field testing at 7 Madrasah; (i) analysis of the field testing on phase two; (j) improvement of the field testing results on phase two. There are two affective domain evaluation instruments developed, namely the instrument of spiritual domain self-assessment intended for madrasah Tsanawiyah students according to their level, namely grade VII, VIII and IX, and the instrument of self-assessment in the domain of social attitudes intended specifically for students of grade VII, VIII and IX. Instruments prepared by each grade are designed by considering competence and content in accordance with the grade level. After phase I and II field testing, overall instruments from grades VII, VIII and IX have met the KMO-MSA (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Measure of Sampling Adequacy) test, as the results are more than half and with a significant value (sig) or the chance (p) is less than a half. As such, the items analysed in the Factor Analysis are eligible to implement.

Based on the data of validity and reliability of affective self-assessment (spiritual domain self-assessment and self-assessment of the domain of social attitudes) above, the instrument is worthy to be used and disseminated. In the 2013 Curriculum implementation, it demands multi techniques use in measuring comprehensive learning outcomes, the resulting instrument can be used as a reference and consideration for teachers in developing learning outcome evaluation instruments in the affective domain of spiritual and social attitudes, especially to measure the achievement of learning outcomes in the domain of social attitudes.

The product instruments can be used to measure the achievement of affective domain learning outcomes in Madrasah Tsanawiyah. In its implementation, measurement needs to be done several times and the person in charge of the educational institution, namely the Head of Madrasah Tsanawiyah and the teachers, can coordinate the right implementation time to take measurements. The content and scope of the instrument can be adjusted in line with the implementation of the content of the 2013 Curriculum.

Recommendations

The product instruments can be used to measure the achievement of affective domain learning outcomes in Madrasah Tsanawiyah. In its implementation, measurement needs to be done several times and the person in charge of the educational institution, namely the Head of Madrasah Tsanawiyah and the teachers, can coordinate the right implementation time to take measurements. The content and scope of the instrument can be adjusted in line with the implementation of the content of the 2013 Curriculum in Indonesia.

Acknowledgements or Notes

This work was supported by State Institute on Islamic Studies of Purwokerto through Budget Implementation List (DIPA) in the year of 2019.

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